

**Towards a common Una Europa RESearch and INnovation
eco-system (Una.Resin)**

D1.2 Una Europa Research & Innovation Strategy

Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	2
INTRODUCTION	3
DEVELOPING THE UNA EUROPA R&I STRATEGY	3
DEVELOPING THE ROADMAP TO IMPLEMENTATION OF THE UNA EUROPA R&I STRATEGY	5
UNA EUROPA RESEARCH & INNOVATION STRATEGY	6
COLLABORATING IN RESEARCH FOR THE FUTURE.....	6
OUR RESEARCH VALUES	7
Diversity and Human Dignity.....	7
Academic Freedom.....	8
Open Research.....	8
Individual Well-Being	8
Delivering Environmental Sustainability.....	8
Ensuring Organisational Resilience.....	8
Acting Globally	8
ADVANCING COLLABORATIVE INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH: AREAS OF ACTION.....	9
1: <i>Strengthening the Una Europa Focus Areas</i>	9
2: <i>Engaging Researchers Broadly</i>	10
3: <i>Opening up Research and Data Infrastructures</i>	11
UNA EUROPA R&I INVESTMENT PATHWAY	13
EUROPEAN FUNDING FOR STRENGTHENING THE FOCUS AREAS AND ENGAGING RESEARCHERS BROADLY	14
<i>Promoting Global Activities</i>	15
<i>Development of Una Europa Signature Projects</i>	15
DIVERSIFYING FUNDING INCOME BEYOND THE EU.....	16
SHARING AND OPENING UP RESEARCH AND DATA INFRASTRUCTURES	16
COMMITMENTS OF THE PARTNER INSTITUTIONS	17
<i>Developing Research Support Networks and Processes</i>	17
<i>A Dedicated Mobility Budget</i>	18
<i>Investing in Digitalising Collaboration</i>	18
<i>Recognition of the Clusters of Research Professionals</i>	19
<i>Permanent Establishment of the Research Coordination Cluster</i>	19
<i>Investing in Seed Funding</i>	20
ROADMAP TO IMPLEMENTATION	21
PHASE I: IDENTIFICATION	21
PHASE II: PRIORITISATION.....	21
PHASE III: IMPLEMENTATION.....	22

Introduction

29th May 2024,: Dr. Elina Tonteri (UH) and Dr. Klaus Wiehl (FUB)

Developing the Una Europa R&I strategy

The Una Europa Alliance, established in 2019, has grown ever since with new collaborative initiatives emerging and a growing body of academics and students engaging in the activities of the Alliance. Not all initiatives were anticipated at the inception of the Una.Resin project plan. Central to our efforts was ensuring that the development of the Una Europa Research & Innovation (R&I) strategy was not done in isolation, but it was a collaborative endeavor, engaging the collective expertise of the Una Europa university community and the Una Europa secretariat, vzw. Most importantly, the Una Europa R&I strategy is closely linked with the broader Una Europa 2030 Strategy. [The Una Europa 2030 Strategy](#) is the culmination of a year-long consultation with our community of students, academics and professional staff to set our course for the future, together. Rooted in our [Manifesto](#), the Strategy sharpens our collective focus on the opportunities and challenges that matter most as we move through the decade ahead.

Concurrent development timelines of these two strategies ensured that the Una.Resin Work Package 1 (WP1) could participate in the preparation of Una Europa 2030 strategy to maintain consistency in goals and activities. This holistic approach to strategic development was designed to also consider and feed into the aims of the Una.Futura project (December 2022 – November 2026), as well as to incorporate new insights and collaborative lessons gleaned from the earlier 1Europe project. We also aligned the strategy development with prevailing European policies. Una.Resin WP4 and Una Europa vzw provided intensive and very valuable support for aligning these complex links to the different aims and activities. The finalized Una Europa R&I Strategy thus stands as a testament to inclusive, well-coordinated policymaking aimed at fostering integrated R&I within the Una Europa Alliance towards the horizon of 2030.

The strategy preparation followed a transparent and solid process, embedded in Una Europa's comprehensive quality assurance mechanisms, in close consultation with strategic alliance governance bodies. The Una.Resin Project Steering Committee (PSC) decided on the operational and resource issues and ensured that the preparation was in line with the other project WPs. Una Europa's Research Strategy Group (RSG), bringing together Vice Rectors for Research Policy (or equivalent) of the eleven partner universities, provided the strategic direction and oversight of this R&I Strategy. The group had a steering role both over the process and the strategy content. The Una Europa Board of Directors (BoD) together with the Una Europa RSG approved the final version of the strategy in their joint meeting in the Una Europa general assembly in June 2023.

The R&I strategy process followed four main steps:

1. **Benchmarking:** The strategy process involved a foundational benchmarking exercise analysing the strategies of the partner universities and collecting information about strategic aims and policies using a questionnaire targeted at senior research professionals at each partner university, an extensive community engagement including six workshops, as well as an online questionnaire open to the whole community of the partner universities collecting insights about the future of the operational environment of the Una Europa R&I ecosystem. These have been described in the Una.Resin D1.1. A notable inclusion was feedback from the Una Europa Diversity Council, emphasizing EDI (equality, diversity, inclusion) considerations within the strategy.
2. **Identifying the key strategic aims and designing the document structure:** It was decided at the Una.Resin PSC that the Una Europa R&I strategy would be the flagship strategy produced in the project and would include

the key messages from the WP2 and WP3 work, even though these WPs also produced their own respective delivery reports: i.e., “Strategy for sharing research infrastructures” (WP2) and “Recommendations for strengthening human capital” (WP3). We carried out a strategic questionnaire of 16 questions targeted at the Una.Resin WP 2-4 leads and co-leads, cluster chairs, and the Una Europa vzw. In the questionnaire, we asked colleagues to identify, considering the Una.Resin aims, outcomes, and insights, 2-4 themes which should be set as strategic priorities when developing services and allocating resources for supporting researchers and/or for institutional or professional development.

The questions addressed the priority strategic themes and key stakeholders, processes, actions, and resources required to satisfy each theme. We also asked about the communication and matchmaking needs, and the cluster learnings and aims. The responders were provided with the following background documents: the Una Europa 2030 strategy; the first milestones to the implementation of the Una Europa 2030 strategy; the Una.Futura project plan; the Una Europa Diversity Council reports: the foregrounding diversity in R&I (2022) and Engaging with Diversity in the European Universities (2022); and the European Universities Initiative (EUI): first lessons, main challenges and perspectives, a study for the European Parliament’s Committee on Culture and Education by the Centre for Higher Education Policy Studies (2023).

In addition, we discussed the key priorities with all Una Europa Focus area self-steering committees and Doctoral Education cluster.

3. **Compilation of the first draft:** The writing process included several WP1 writing sessions both onsite and online. This first version was structured in the fashion so that the Una Europa 2030 Strategy provided the broad strategic base and the Una Europa R&I Strategy acted as a next step to implementation describing also actions identified under the strategic aims and resourcing recommendations. The Una Europa vzw provided feedback considering the 1Europe outcomes and Una.Futura plans. We presented the first version to the RSG and BoD on the 29th March 2023.
4. **Writing the second draft version of the Una Europa R&I strategy and finalisation:** In their meeting on the 29th March 2023, the Una Europa RSG and BoD agreed with the strategic aims and values presented in the document but requested revision of the document structure. Thus, we revised the document and, as a result, the final version had three parts: 1) The Una Europa R&I strategy; 2) Annex 1: The Una Europa R&I Investment Pathway; 3) Annex 2: The Roadmap to Implementation.

This version where strategic aims and implementation actions were distinctly outlined was approved by the PSC, RSG and BoD as the final version of the Una Europa General Assembly in Leiden on the 6th-7th of June 2023.

Figure 1: Key groups that participated in the Una Europa R&I strategy writing process

Developing the roadmap to implementation of the Una Europa R&I strategy

During the strategy development process, we identified areas of activities and individual activities that would be needed to build a sustainable support for our academic community towards 2030. These provided a base for the Roadmap to Implementation of the Una Europa R&I strategy presented in the Annex 2. We also identified resourcing needs and potential resourcing sources presented in Annex 1, the Una Europa R&I Investment Pathway.

In order to ensure the long-term sustainability of key activities initiated under the Una.Resin project, Una Europa took a two-pronged approach. On the one hand, the strategic decision was made to take a holistic approach in the Una.Futura project (Erasmus+ programme, 2022 - 2026). This entailed the integration of key Una.Resin project outcomes across the whole body of the proposed project, including a dedicated Work Package, co-led by the Una.Resin Coordinating Institution and developing the Una Europa Research & Innovation Vision and action plan. On the other hand, the final year of Una.Resin saw the launch of the Una Europa Research & Innovation matrix exercise. This exercise was designed to facilitate a prioritization exercise at the highest decision-making levels of the alliance and provide advice for the Una Europa R&I action plan.

The activities proposed in the R&I matrix exercise represented those identified in the Una.Resin project but mirrored also the ambitions expressed in the Una Europa Research & Innovation Vision, which distills and frames the comprehensive Una Europa Research & Innovation Strategy at hand in a future-oriented way. The R&I matrix exercise is anchored in three strategic overarching objectives: Objective 1: Support for the development of Una Europa's international hubs for research, education and knowledge transfer; Objective 2: Providing an international framework for training targeted at Una Europa early career researchers and Objective 3: Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research infrastructure Ecosystem.

A dedicated online survey was designed to allow partner universities to make strategic choices in an open and transparent manner. This process took place between June and September 2023. The results of the survey were subsequently processed and interpreted centrally by Una Europa vzw, together with select colleagues from the Una.Resin project who helped to design the exercise. These results were then presented to the Una Europa Research Strategy Group at a virtual meeting in October 2023. Subsequently, a physical meeting of the Una Europa Research Strategy Group and Board of Directors was utilized for a discussion in relation to the potential levels of ambition and levels of resourcing required to ensure the implementation of the chosen activities. A dedicated R&I Action Plan that will foresee all agreed modes of implementation is expected to be signed off by Una Europa leadership in June 2024.

Figure 2: Governance bodies and projects included in the on-going matrix exercise.

Una Europa Research & Innovation Strategy

Una.Resin Project Deliverable D1.2

Final Version, 23rd June 2023; Lead Authors: Dr. Elina Tonteri (UH) and Dr. Carolin F. Roeder (FUB)

Collaborating in Research for the Future

Freie Universität Berlin | Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna | University College Dublin/An Coláiste Ollscoile Baile Átha Cliath | University of Edinburgh | Helsingin yliopisto/Helsingfors universitet | Uniwersytet Jagielloński w Krakowie | Universiteit Leiden | KU Leuven | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne | Universität Zürich have joined forces as Una Europa, a unique alliance of leading European universities. Together, we represent one of the strongest research-intensive European University Alliances of its kind. Since its establishment in 2019, the Alliance has grown in size, gathered valuable experience, and deepened collaboration through EU-funded projects and other strategic initiatives developed by our partner universities.

Una Europa's ambition is to create a European inter-university campus that encompasses education, research, innovation and societal outreach in a holistic manner. Embracing institutional and cultural diversity, our goal is to foster the sharing of physical and digital spaces, infrastructure, resources, and best practices to collectively pursue excellence. Our Alliance is founded on long-standing collaboration and strong connections across various initiatives and stakeholders. We are committed to establishing a framework for systematic collaboration seamlessly integrated into institutional structures and workflows, bolstering research and innovation capabilities also through professional and institutional capacity building. The networks of dedicated professional staff, a hallmark of Una Europa's innovative approach, serve as the backbone of our alliance, providing expertise and support for our collaborative endeavours.

Large-scale research collaboration plays a vital role in tackling the complex and ever-evolving global challenges confronting our planet. These challenges require insights that transcend the limitations of individual research questions. As research-intensive universities, we are at the forefront of generating profound knowledge and innovative solutions to address the intractable issues of our time and future. With our extensive network of global partners, Una Europa presents a unique opportunity to leverage our complementary strengths and engage in cutting-edge collaborative research. Together, we have the potential to achieve meaningful outcomes for our societies and the world at large.

Our Alliance's vision for the current decade is set by the Una 2030 Strategy. The strategy identifies institutional priorities within three strategic pillars that ensure sustained collaboration beyond the lifespan of individual projects:

- I: Enhancing collaboration in research and innovation.
- II: Consolidating a future education model rooted in challenges, research, and interdisciplinarity.
- III: Promoting innovative science communication and strengthening public engagement.

Building upon these pillars, this Research & Innovation Strategy sets out the following strategic areas of action required to cultivate a research and innovation ecosystem that promotes collaborative interdisciplinary research by 2030:

- 1: Strengthening the Una Europa Focus Areas
 - Establishing Interdisciplinary Hubs

- Training Researchers of the Future
- Strengthening Collaboration Beyond Academia

2: Engaging Researchers Broadly

- Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives
- Promoting Mobility and Community Building
- Digitalising Collaboration

3: Opening up Research and Data Infrastructures

- Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration
- Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills
- Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructure Ecosystem

Each area of activity also embraces crosscutting values that form the foundation of our shared identity as a values-driven Alliance. These values shape our research approach and align with the institutional priorities outlined in the 2030 Strategy. They encompass diversity and human dignity, academic freedom, open research, individual well-being, environmental sustainability, organisational resilience, and global engagement.

The Una Europa R&I Investment Pathway for Research & Innovation (Annex 1) outlines both internal and external resources required for implementation of the strategic goals. Additionally, the Una Europa Roadmap to implementation aims to establishing sustainable links between individual actions and current and future Una Europa projects, such as Una.Futura (Annex 2). However, achieving our ambitious vision for research collaboration necessitates interventions also at the policy level. The European Universities Initiative (EUI) is a unique undertaking that calls for adjustments and long-term commitment at both the European and national levels. While the European Strategy for Universities recognises the European University alliances as the flagships of an innovative, globally competitive, and attractive European Education Area (EEA) and European Research Area (ERA), navigating the complex policy and funding landscape at regional, national, and European levels remains challenging. These challenges must be addressed to facilitate seamless transnational collaboration and ensure a sustainable future for the EUI.

Hence, a more streamlined and strategic approach to policy and funding is essential to support the long-term strategic collaborations of higher education institutions and foster excellence in European higher education, R&I. Una Europa will advocate for additional European funding instruments that promote interdisciplinary research of broad scope and investigator-driven nature. We will also seek instruments tailored to the unique needs of research infrastructures in higher education, particularly small and medium-sized ones that require adequate funding to unlock their full potential. Europe must ensure that funding instruments address the pressing needs in research and leverage the expertise of the research community to identify the shortcomings of current top-down funding calls.

Our Research Values

Diversity and Human Dignity

Una Europa is united in diversity. Diversity, taken as a concept, acknowledges the multidimensional differences between people that are shaped by social categories. We firmly believe that diversity, equity, and inclusion are essential prerequisites for fostering truly excellent research. Guided by the expertise of our Diversity Council, we are dedicated to integrating diversity considerations in all of our programs and actions. While our prestigious institutions have a proven ability to attract world-class talent, we critically assess the existing conditions for success and strive to create an environment where diverse talents can flourish within our multilingual setting. We are also committed to breaking down implicit hierarchical distinctions between academic and professional staff and fostering genuine team-based approaches to research.

Academic Freedom

As representatives of leading publicly funded research-intensive institutions of higher education, we wholeheartedly uphold the principles of academic freedom, ethical research, truth, integrity, and inclusivity. Our community is fuelled by the intrinsic curiosity that drives bottom-up exploration and recognises the inseparable connection between education and research. Embracing the essence of academic freedom, we are committed to empowering our researchers to embark on bold and unconventional ventures that transcend conventional methodologies.

Open Research

Una Europa embraces the principles of open research across all levels of collaboration and training, while taking into account the specific needs of different disciplines. We strive to establish a framework for open research that serves as a catalyst for strategic decision-making, innovative methodologies, and fruitful collaborations among institutions and researchers. Our strategic priorities align with the ambitions of the European Union's Open Science policy, particularly in the domains of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), open data sharing, open access to publications, the European Open Science Cloud, mutual learning, education and skills, as well as citizen science. Committed to fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration between universities and non-academic stakeholders, including citizens and industry, we value open dialogue that embraces diverse perspectives. By actively engaging with different communities, we seek to mutually benefit from collaboration and contribute to the advancement of knowledge and societal progress.

Individual Well-Being

Individual well-being is paramount in enabling students, researchers, teachers, and professional staff to thrive. Una Europa is deeply committed to cultivating an environment where individuals can reach their full potential. We prioritise the promotion of work-life balance, diverse career opportunities, fair policies, and people-centric procedures. These commitments extend to all aspects of our Alliance, ensuring the well-being and fulfilment of our community members.

Delivering Environmental Sustainability

Sustainability, in all its aspects, lies at the heart of Una Europa's mission. It serves as a fundamental objective within the Una Europa 2030 Strategy and permeates our research and teaching priorities, governance, and work processes. To solidify our commitment to sustainability, we have established the Una Europa Sustainability and Climate Protection Task Force. This task force harnesses its expertise to guide our community in integrating the United Nations' agenda for the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into their daily endeavours, as well as in the creation of innovative projects and formats.

Ensuring Organisational Resilience

To promote financial and institutional resilience, our collaboration approach adheres to principles of efficiency, effectiveness, simplicity, scalability, and feasibility. We prioritise areas where collaboration yields significant added value and remain dedicated to streamlined processes. We incentivise researchers and professionals alike to actively contribute to shaping the vibrant Una Europa research community.

Acting Globally

Una Europa institutions are global actors, and as an Alliance, we have an even broader reach. Understanding this reach as a responsibility and opportunity to address global challenges from diverse perspectives, Una Europa aims to establish multi-lateral global partnerships and engage with global talent. We intend to collaborate with our international strategic partners for mutual benefit, leveraging synergies and expertise from all parties involved. Our open approach to collaboration with higher education institutions in Africa is gradually taking shape and will serve as a foundation and inspiration for further consolidating and exploring joint collaborations with other like-minded universities in different regions of the world, such as Latin America.

Advancing Collaborative Interdisciplinary Research: Areas of Action

1: Strengthening the Una Europa Focus Areas

Una Europa, as a community deeply committed to long-term collaboration and endowed with a wealth of talented individuals, is uniquely positioned to foster collaboration among researchers from diverse cultural backgrounds who explore shared topics through distinct disciplinary lenses. The Una Europa Focus Areas represent interdisciplinary fields that unite researchers from partner institutions across a wide spectrum of disciplines. Our support services and policies will prioritise promoting academic collaboration within these areas, empowering researchers to jointly pursue basic and applied research to tackle complex challenges.

Until 2030, the Alliance has chosen the following Focus Areas: Cultural Heritage, Sustainability, Data Science and Artificial Intelligence, Europe and the World, One Health, and Future Materials. These areas reflect some of the most pressing global and societal challenges and high-level priorities of the European Union. Simultaneously, they allow intrinsic curiosity and innovation necessary for addressing emerging challenges in the future.

Establishing Interdisciplinary Hubs

In the coming years, the academic Self-steering Committees (SSCs) of the Focus Areas will undergo a transformation into interdisciplinary hubs. These hubs will actively engage the wider Una Europa community, fostering academic collaboration not only within the Alliance but also with global partners. This transformation aims to realize our ambition of addressing education, R&I, and societal outreach in a comprehensive manner. The priorities set by the SSCs will guide the development of Una Europa support networks and the Investment Pathway, which will identify the necessary resources for the successful implementation of these activities.

The SSCs, in collaboration with the professional staff, will work towards the development of **Una Europa signature formats** for education and research within our Alliance. These formats can be applied across different Focus Areas and encompass activities such as summer and winter schools, research semesters, grant matchmaking, science events, digital catalogues, and programs focused on transversal skills. By establishing these common formats, we can establish robust processes for support, resource allocation, and communication. Additionally, these formats create valuable opportunities for academics to come together, fostering cross-disciplinary collaboration and generating new research ideas across various career stages.

Una Europa distinguishes itself as an Alliance of research universities that house influential research centres, institutes, and initiatives committed to interdisciplinary approaches. Several of these initiatives are explicitly designed to foster multi-, trans-, or interdisciplinary research. By strengthening **collaboration among these existing initiatives** and fostering connections with the Una Europa Focus Areas, our Alliance aspires to become a trailblazer in large-scale collaborative research and set a benchmark for the European Research Area.

When considering the **establishment of new Una Europa Focus Areas**, several important factors will guide the decision-making process. These factors include the potential of the suggested Focus Area to attract researchers from diverse disciplines, its capacity to become a leader in the field of inquiry, opportunities for collaboration with existing interdisciplinary initiatives and centres, and its potential to facilitate joint formats. Throughout this process, we will foster active participation and exchange of ideas by engaging our broad research community, specific stakeholders, and the Una Europa's Future UniLab.

Training Researchers of the Future

Being the future of academia, early-career researchers play a pivotal role in shaping the research landscape of tomorrow. With our ability to offer a wide range of training opportunities across partner institutions, Una Europa is

uniquely positioned to empower this vital demographic with the skills and knowledge they need to thrive in the evolving academic environment and diversify their career opportunities. As such, investing in the training of early-career researchers is a strategic priority for Una Europa.

Una Europa will continue developing **joint educational formats** that promote the acquisition of **interdisciplinary skills and collaborative research**. This work necessitates the command of different research methods, epistemological frameworks, and publishing cultures. Moreover, the dynamics and timeframes of interdisciplinary research collaboration differ from research based on the single disciplinary tradition. In all Una Europa signature projects, doctoral students will be included early on to grow their knowledge of **collaborative research**. To promote interdisciplinary research, we urgently need to address the **career risks** that early-career researchers are particularly exposed to when pursuing interdisciplinary projects. To this end, the Una Europa partners will seek solutions to the challenges of the interdisciplinary academic positions in university departments as defined by the traditional disciplines.

Our goal is to ensure that **open research** becomes second nature to all our researchers. To achieve this, we aim to provide the necessary skills training to incorporate open research routines and practices seamlessly into their work. This will include guidance on how to evaluate research outputs without relying on traditional metrics like journal impact factor, methods of citizen science and research FAIR data management skills. Training shall be integrated into educational pathways and relevant activities of the Focus Areas.

The very principles of **research assessment** require reform to allow our researchers to conduct the research of the future: bold, diversified, collaborative, and impactful. We are committed to promoting the inclusion of interdisciplinary research, open science and collaboration with society and industry as markers of excellence in research assessment. As part of this commitment, Una Europa supports research assessment reform endeavors such as the Agreement of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment, of which many of our partner universities are signatories.

Strengthening Collaboration Beyond Academia

Breaking down disciplinary thinking through collaborative research in our Focus Areas is fundamental to develop comprehensive solutions to societal challenges. Equally important is the collaboration with non-academic partners to ensure the transfer of knowledge and the application of research findings in society. This is also recognised by grant agencies which increasingly ask for stakeholder inclusion. Una Europa is hence committed to fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration between university and non-academic actors, including citizens and industry. Through open dialogue, we seek to address the perspectives of diverse communities and bring the benefit of collaboration to both sides.

Together, the eco-systems of our partner universities offer a unique opportunity for collaborative research teams to establish new relations with non-academic partners. Nurturing partnerships with non-academic actors demands the dedicated commitment of numerous individuals, with the rewards often materialising over the long haul. To fully harness the strengths of our diverse ecosystems, our knowledge and technology transfer services will jointly support Una Europa projects during and after the pre-award phase. Moreover, our objective is to consolidate resources to create training programs focused on impactful public engagement. These programs will encompass different transfer formats including citizen science, science communication, and policy advocacy, and will be seamlessly integrated into our Una Europa educational formats. By doing so, we will open new avenues of knowledge transfer and foster the development of social and technological innovations.

2: Engaging Researchers Broadly

Una Europa is an Alliance by and for every member of our partner universities. Along with supporting the Focus Areas, we are committed to become an inspiring and well-established collaboration framework for researchers of our partners broadly. In that way, we can promote EDI in research, which is crucial for ensuring that research reflects the perspectives and experiences of a diverse range of people from all disciplines, career stages and backgrounds.

Supporting Bottom-Up Research

Una Europa nurtures bold research that pursues new avenues. To support this within but also beyond the Focus Areas, Una Europa will develop tools to **incentivise bottom-up research initiatives** and **broaden the involvement of researchers**. This will include regular seed-funding calls, facilitation of funding-specific matchmaking actions and distribution of national funding opportunities. By means of systematic and effective communication through central and institutional channels, we aim to increase the distribution of Una Europa opportunities.

Promoting Mobility and Community Building

Una Europa provides an unmatched opportunity for researchers to flourish in an international, intercultural environment. Through our Alliance, researchers of any stage can **diversify and grow their disciplinary and interdisciplinary networks**. Una Europa encourages low-threshold informal connections by the virtue of membership in the Alliance and will, in addition, strategically support community building. Not only in getting together, but in doing something together lies the true value of our Alliance.

Firstly, community building is encouraged through the many virtual and physical **Una Europa signature activities**—ranging from summer schools to Una Europa talks and gatherings. These events are opportunities to promote valuable exchange between research professionals and researchers. Secondly, we will continue to enhance the institutional capacity to invest in mobility opportunities. Una Europa will develop a joint virtual and physical **mobility framework** for students, researchers and professional staff, including both short- and long-term mobility, and explore and utilise existing EU and national mobility schemes. We will put specific emphasis on creating possibilities for exchanges as visiting scholars and through the Una Chairs and the joint Institute for Advanced Studies initiatives. Moreover, Una Europa will develop coordinated support for Marie Curie fellowship opportunities for early-career researchers. The Alliance is also committed to systematically **sharing information on career and funding opportunities** at Una Europa institutions, including national schemes available for early-career researchers coming both from EU and non-EU countries. In the long-term, Una Europa will develop **mentoring programs** for early-career researchers and research professionals who will be matched with a mentor from a Una Europa member institution or one of our partners.

Digitalising Collaboration

Digitising collaboration is crucial to build a sustainable, ever-closer community. Our aim is to develop a comprehensive virtual platform which will aid community building across all Una Europa groups, address research-specific needs and host already existing or newly developed online training courses for researchers and research professionals. To meet the needs of current collaborative Una Europa research projects in a timely manner, such as cloud storage, sharing expressions of interest for funding calls and navigation to our partner universities' research portals, Una Europa will expand the utility of the Una Europa website and deploy commercially and publicly available products. In the medium term, we require a tool for sharing information on research and data infrastructures. In the long term, we aim to further facilitate efficient matchmaking between researchers, research groups, and interdisciplinary units by developing AI-based tools that collect data from our partner universities' research portals, also addressing the legal barriers.

3: Opening up Research and Data Infrastructures

Una Europa acknowledges the pivotal role of research and data infrastructures in driving collaborative research. We are committed to promoting the accessibility and interoperability of research infrastructures within our Alliance as well as facilitating the storage, sharing, and data access to enhance research capacity, foster collaboration across the Alliance and beyond, and ensure the long-term sustainability of research infrastructures that are essential to research activities in our Focus Areas. To comprehensively address these aspects, we have developed the Una Europa Research Infrastructure Strategy, which outlines a common framework of actions structured around the following three key initiatives.

Promoting Openness of Research Infrastructures to Foster Research Collaboration

To promote the openness of RIs and data infrastructures, we aim to coordinate efforts in overcoming legal, financial, organisational, technical and cultural barriers that restrict the sharing of research and data infrastructures within and across institutions. We will conduct a **comprehensive analysis of barriers and enablers**, including an in-depth investigation of costing/business models and legal issues related to opening and sharing data, especially clinical data. The insights gained from this analysis will inform the development of common solutions, guiding principles, and scalable models, which will be incorporated into a Una Europa Charter for RIs.

We will also support the development of a strong **research infrastructure community** through physical mobility, networking, matchmaking formats, and the exchange of best practices. These initiatives will foster structured synergies in specific thematic areas and contribute to the effective management of research infrastructure across and beyond the Alliance. Additionally, we will establish a data community to operationalize FAIR data principles at both theme-specific and institutional levels.

Furthermore, we will collaboratively create **tools for sharing information on Una Europa research infrastructures**, facilitating cross-institutional access and visibility for external users, including actors from the private, public sector, and civil society. To achieve this, we will develop in the medium to long term a common Una Europa digital catalogue of RIs and a portal of services.

Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills

Sharing infrastructures will incentivise networking and training, benefiting our entire research community. We will strategically invest in continuously **advancing the skills** of our research infrastructure managers and data experts. Our approach will involve mutual learning processes within the research infrastructures and data community, adopting a peer learning approach. This will include exchange of knowledge and best practices through virtual, and physical mobility and processes towards more structured mobility and exchange formats. Additionally, we will establish training activities for the RIs and data community, collaborating with projects such as RiTrainPlus, to create structured training programs that **facilitate career paths and professional development** in research infrastructure and data management.

Developing a Stronger and Integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructure Ecosystem

To develop a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructures Ecosystem, we aim to adopt joint visions for opening and sharing of research infrastructures, working towards the promotion of **common guiding principles** outlined in the Una Europa Charter for research infrastructures. In addition, we will engage to raising the awareness of actions that can drive a broader cultural change and promote openness fostering collaborative research. Furthermore, we will **advocate for improved research infrastructure policies and funding landscape at the European level**, with a specific focus on supporting small-medium sized research infrastructures that are characteristic of higher education institutions. This will be done by creating synergy with the initiatives of relevant research associations and in collaboration with other European University alliances.

Una Europa R&I Investment Pathway

Annex 1, Una.Resin Project Deliverable D1.2

Final Version, 23rd June 2023; Lead authors: Dr. Elina Tonteri (Una.Resin, UH), Kristof Vlaeminck (Una Europa VZW) and Sophia Karner (Una Europa VZW)

This Investment Pathway identifies funding avenues for implementing the three strategic areas of action set in the Una Europa R&I strategy: i.e., Strengthening the Una Europa Focus Areas, Engaging Researchers Broadly and Opening up Research and Data Infrastructures. Systematic support for the identification of external R&I funding opportunities is a pivotal pillar of a sound R&I ecosystem. As such, this document provides a view to utilising external funding opportunities for R&I – whether at national, European or international levels – and advises the development of the holistic Una Europa External Funding Strategy. In addition to the external funding, internal commitments from the partner institutions are needed. We present areas of investment that are required from the member institutions to fully promote the aims set for collaborative interdisciplinary research by 2030.

Alongside this Investment Pathway, the Una Europa Roadmap for R&I aims to establish sustainable links between individual actions driving the R&I collaboration in our Alliance and the on-going Una.Futura project. Furthermore, the roadmap process aims to identify essential activities, where the Alliance has ambition, but which go beyond the on-going project frameworks.

Such funding pathway cannot exist in isolation and is inevitably influenced by European policy and funding priorities. In turn, it must be harnessed as a tool to shape those external funding and policy agendas with a view to creating a more enabling policy and funding environment at national, European, and international levels in the future. Una Europa is engaged in constantly reviewing the relevance of our own processes and policies and in turn providing our contributions for the best of European research.

We are committed to establishing a framework for systematic collaboration seamlessly integrated into institutional structures and workflows, bolstering R&I capabilities also through professional and institutional capacity building. Thus, in addition to the support to the academic community, resourcing of institutional capacity building and professional development is addressed in this Investment Pathway. The Una.Resin project has led to tangible progress in a number of areas, including the creation of the Alliance's first joint R&I Strategy. In addition, the project has led to the creation of a network of professional experts, such as the establishment of the Una Europa Clusters, with institutional and technical expertise continuing to act as the backbone of this collaboration. To be able to build on these first important results, we will continue institutional capacity building. However, the three-year duration of the project limits the concrete impact at institutional levels, which is a much more long-term process that transcends this period of EU funding. Further support within the upcoming period of the R&I programmes is key for creating a true European inter-university campus that encompasses education, R&I and societal outreach in a holistic manner. Una Europa calls for support for a true European Excellence Initiative that provides systematic and long-term support to higher education institutions in all parts of the ERA. This action must be designed with a view to driving the visibility and global competitiveness of Europe's strongest higher education institutions on the world stage. It should further include a strong component for targeted R&I actions.

European Funding for Strengthening the Focus Areas and Engaging Researchers Broadly

Una Europa is committed to driving forward the transformation of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) and contributing to the objectives of the European Research Area (ERA) to fully accommodate the ambitions behind seamless transnational collaboration. Going forward, Una Europa will go beyond creating mere synergies of its education and R&I dimension and advocating for a more streamlined and strategic policy and funding approach towards supporting higher education institutions as pivotal actors of the ERA in the future.

Founded in 2019, the Alliance has successfully secured projects in successive rounds of EU funding. In just three years, the Alliance's pilot projects have provided the direction for the launch of numerous joint educational and research programmes as well as the development of a shared R&I agenda transcending boundaries of discipline, institution, and country to take international collaboration to the next level. Una Europa aims to continue to develop ties and close collaboration with academic and non-academic actors from local, national, and global environments, and become an institution which is firmly rooted in a rich ecosystem, thus enabling us to secure the resources, adapt to changing conditions and truly contribute to social development.

European funding continues to be the priority funding scheme, when building the Una Europa R&I ecosystem. We are committed to developing robust processes for our research community to find sufficient resources to conduct bold collaborative research. To maximise our success, the Una Europa External Funding Strategy should reflect the aims of the Una Europa Focus Areas and outline comprehensively the relevant opportunities across EU funding programmes, notably Horizon Europe, Erasmus+, and Digital Europe. It should also consider targeted EU instruments in the areas of regional development (structural funding), investment, recovery, and resilience, including the analysis of possible synergies across programmes.

In the following years, we will prioritise building robust processes for the Horizon Europe Pillar II calls. To incentivise the creation of a broad innovation ecosystem, we aim to find ways to engage our knowledge and technology transfer services to jointly support Una Europa projects during and after the pre-award phase to identify the most relevant non-academic partners. To further strengthen our ecosystem, the Una Europa External Funding Strategy should address opportunities in frameworks like the New European Innovation Agenda and Horizon Europe Pillar III. In the future, the Alliance needs to consider ways to strategically advocate for areas of new partnerships and national co-funding to the relevant initiatives. Una Europa should also seek opportunities to fund the education of the future researchers in the Una Europa Focus Areas with the MSCA Doctoral Networks instrument.

As outlined also in the Una Europa Position Paper on the EU R&I framework programmes launched earlier this year, Una Europa advocates for EC investment in collaborative funding instruments to solve grand challenges and incentivise bottom-up research collaboration. We suggest a shift from top-down instruments towards more bottom-up collaborative opportunities that are as open as possible in scope and allow for interdisciplinary research perspectives that are needed to develop a true incentive for deep, long-term collaboration in a transnational context. The role of research universities in strengthening long-term basic research as a basis for innovation and solving grand challenges must be recognised. Individual researchers, who share this strong commitment to solving the grand challenges of our time, need to be given the space to define the scope of their own research, to ensure the most impactful and innovative research outcomes. The next Horizon Europe Strategic Plan should thus focus on enhancing interdisciplinary research across intervention areas and more importantly across the six Clusters in Pillar II. In addition, a strategic approach to incentivise and reward interdisciplinarity in collaborative projects should be developed in the long-term.

Promoting Global Activities

Una Europa institutions are global actors, and as an Alliance, we have an even broader reach. Understanding this reach as a responsibility and opportunity to address global challenges from diverse perspectives, Una Europa aims to establish multi-lateral global partnerships and engage with global talent. The collaboration with the Una Europa strategic partner higher education institutions in Africa is progressively taking shape. This approach can serve as a basis and inspiration for consolidating and exploring joint Una Europa collaborations with other like-minded universities in other priority regions across the globe. Going forward, Una Europa aims to initiate a more in-depth exploration of collaborations with higher education institutions in Latin America.

It is important to start identifying possible funding avenues for these collaborations. The EU policy agenda, as articulated in the EU's Global Approach for R&I as well as the EU-AU Strategic Agenda, is reflected in current and future EU funding instruments, such as the EU-AU Innovation Agenda, the Africa Initiative in Horizon Europe as well as the geographical focus in EU framework programmes more broadly. In addition, funding will be allocated for Sub-Saharan Africa under the EU's new financial instrument the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI) – 'Global Europe' for the period 2021-2027. NDICI-Global Europe now incorporates the cooperation with Africa, the Caribbean and the Pacific into the budget. The EU also has a long-standing strategic partnership with Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC), which is of high geostrategic relevance. For the period 2021-27, the NDICI-Global Europe foresees funding programs for the LAC region, for country and regional programmes. In addition, the EU supports initiatives highly relevant for the Una Europa research community like those promoting democracy and human rights, peace and security as well as the region's participation in addressing global challenges, such as climate change, through dedicated thematic programmes.

Una Europa emphasises openness to the world of present and future European R&I programmes. It is essential to recognise that research collaboration knows no boundaries, which is why future European funding must be as open as possible to allow for close collaboration between higher education institutions irrespective of their geographical location. Una Europa suggests increasing association agreements for future R&I programmes to include more countries across the globe. We particularly call for a smooth association of the United Kingdom and Switzerland, as two our partner universities are located in these countries.

Development of Una Europa Signature Projects

The development of top-down signature projects at the level of Una Europa is essential both to ensure the long-term sustainability of the Alliance as a whole, as well as support concrete next steps towards the Alliance's vision in the area of R&I. Such strategic projects must not only be fully aligned with Una Europa's objectives, but also fulfil a number of important quality assurance criteria that guarantee that ambitions are kept high: they must be of added value, focusing on those activities that can be realised better together rather than as separate institutions; enhance the quality of the Alliance as a whole or the individual institutions; be seen as innovative; be transformative, aiming to bring about deep and future-proof transformations; and serve to promote common European values as a basis of interdisciplinary, intercultural and international collaboration.

The aim to submit an Una Europa COFUND project proposal under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) of Horizon Europe in 2024 is an example of such an Una Europa signature project. This proposal is developed under the leadership of Una Europa vzw as coordinator with the strong involvement of COFUND experts from across the Una Europa partner institutions showing concretely the added value of networking allowing ad hoc task forces to work on the proposals on basis of the established workflows at each of the participating partner university.

Una Europa vzw, strategically located in Brussels, advocates for Una Europa's interests at European level and ensures a close and continuous dialogue with European policymakers at various stages of the policy-making cycle. In addition, Una Europa vzw seeks to influence present and future R&I framework programmes from the outset, advocating for meaningful and long-term support for European University Alliances. Una Europa vzw is thus ideally placed to oversee such signature projects at the level of the Alliance, in close collaboration with select experts across the Una Europa partner institutions.

Diversifying Funding Income Beyond the EU

While EU funding will remain a major external funding source to support Una Europa's R&I dimension, the Alliance will also explore funding beyond the EU Framework Programmes. This is particularly relevant since two Una Europa partner universities are in non-member states, United Kingdom and Switzerland. Diversifying funding income beyond the sources of the EC will not only breed financial sustainability, but also underpin Una Europa's global ambitions.

Una Europa is engaged to develop joint approach towards disseminating information on relevant local, regional, and national funding opportunities that are available to international applicants. Una Europa Research Coordination Cluster (RCC) members, together with their colleagues, will identify and advertise such opportunities using the digital tools provided by Una Europa, as well as institutional communication channels at the partner universities. To better prepare early-career researchers for positions at other Una Europa partner universities or within their own institution, the RCC members will organise annual or bi-annual information sessions about the various national funding landscapes and peculiarities of the national career paths.

Going forward, Una Europa will consider untapped sources of corporate funding as well as philanthropy more closely, which may provide support for specific R&I activities. The Alliance's prestigious heritage brands and the Una Europa sign of quality are expected to attract interest from corporate organisations and philanthropic institutions. We already have an encouraging example of this in the One Health Focus Area, where a company saw remarkable added value in the possibility to approach the Una Europa network rather than the universities separately.

Sharing and Opening up Research and Data Infrastructures

The Una Europa R&I strategy outlines three key areas fostering sharing and opening the data and research infrastructures that are described in depth in the Una Europa Research Infrastructure Strategy being developed as part of the Una.Resin project. The actions to fulfil the strategic aims require, first of all, institutional commitment of the Una Europa universities in terms of human and financial resources, to support training activities on research infrastructures and promote the consolidation of FAIR data principles, exchange of knowledge and best practices, the activities of specific working groups, community building actions and the creation of meaningful synergies with relevant initiatives, such as open data networks. As for more ambitious actions that could be carried out in the medium-long term - such as developing a common catalogue of research infrastructures and portal of services and implementing a Una Europa Charter for research infrastructures -, dedicated sustainable funding for the Alliance at the European level is required.

Mobility is essential for mutual learning and training. The mobility schemes will be planned out in line with the Una.Futura project and will also be supported through joint applications under the Erasmus+ programme. Moreover, the Una Europa universities are encouraged to identify opportunities for external funding aimed at the professional development of research infrastructure managers and data experts in the framework of Horizon Europe (e.g., under the WIDERA calls), also in collaboration for instance with the RiTrain Plus project. The Una Europa universities will also explore regional and national opportunities for funding in-person visits and covering open-access fees; this will encourage future research collaborations and joint applications to Horizon Europe and other funding programs.

However, it is important to underline that research infrastructures face several challenges in terms of funding: lack of dedicated long-term recurring subsidies; extreme fragmentation of funding mechanisms, relative absence of funding for small and medium-sized research infrastructures. This represents an important bottleneck for the sustainability of research infrastructures and for opening and sharing research infrastructures. Opening and sharing research and data

infrastructures at the Alliance level also towards external actors will require improvements in the European funding landscape for research infrastructures, including funding instruments for training.

Commitments of the Partner Institutions

Una Europa builds long-term collaboration that reaches beyond the lifecycle of single projects and is positioned to establish complex links between different actions and actors. We will build a framework for systematic collaboration that is integrated into institutional structures and workflows calling not only direct funding for research collaboration, but also resourcing for enhancing capacities through professional and institutional development. We also recognise the need for re-thinking how we can collectively enhance mutual learning for the benefit of our institutions, the Alliance, and the whole of Europe.

These resourcing priorities are partly outlined in the visions and action plans of the Una Europa Transversal Themes developed currently in the Una.Futura project. However, there are specific needs for the R&I dimension that go beyond project scopes and need to be further addressed. As public funding of higher education institutions is declining in many of our partners' countries, prioritising R&I support actions by partner institutions requires careful consideration. This will be done in the implementation phase of the R&I strategy as described by the Una Europa R&I Roadmap (Annex 2).

Developing Research Support Networks and Processes

With its headquarters in Brussels, Una Europa vzw is uniquely positioned to provide early intelligence on European funding programmes, a vital task for the early preparation of common proposals. Setting the benchmark, Una.Resin has successfully developed and piloted match-making formats for researchers targeted at Pillar II calls of Horizon Europe as well as an on-line workshop format to collect insights on emerging research topics. Una Europa will scale up these formats to maximise the development of insightful groundbreaking project proposals for Horizon Europe and other external funding programmes. Una Europa will also develop processes and identify professional networks at the partner universities to identify non-academic actors as part of the matchmaking. This will not only be key for building impactful projects, but also for creating a truly international ecosystem of the European research universities and the non-academic actors. As a next step, Una Europa aims to also utilise the learnings from the above-mentioned pilots and organise virtual match-making workshops on selected calls within the Horizon Europe Africa Initiative to broaden the research collaboration with our African strategic partners.

In addition to digital tools, workshop formats, and clear processes, Una Europa requires expert staff for facilitation and coordination. Una Europa as an Alliance will focus on collaborative activities, identifying relevant funding opportunities and matchmaking of researchers. The matchmaking phase will include general training on different funding instruments and best practices of grant writing. While the role of the Una Europa External Funding Officer is to identify external funding opportunities for the research community together with the academic SSCs of the Una Europa Focus Areas and initiate the matchmaking processes, the RCC will provide intelligence and initiate the process at institutional level. Most importantly, the RCC members will support the External Funding Officer and the SSC members in identifying potential coordinating senior researchers for large-scale project proposals. The RCC will also have a leading role in informing researchers at their home institution about opportunities during the expressions of interest (EoI) phase. This information should be advertised both via Una Europa and institutional channels. EoIs should be publicised on the shared Una Europa digital platform. Furthermore, the RCC will aid in appointing facilitators for the matchmaking workshops.

After the matchmaking phase, the proposal process will be handed over to the universities preparing the proposal following the support processes and policies of the coordinating partner. Proposal preparation may require collaboration of the academics, funding professionals of the participating universities, as well as grant writing experts, financial support staff, and HR. Overall, networking of these groups within Una Europa and mutual learning in the processes of preparing joint proposals has a clear added value for the Alliance and for the partner institutions.

A Dedicated Mobility Budget

Our Alliance has recently launched an Una Europa Vision and Action Plan on Mobility. This plan highlights that mobility is not a goal but a means to realise the visionary idea of a European Campus. The vision aims to make an impact beyond projects- not only students, academics, and professional services staff, but also on present and future European policies on higher education and research. Mobility is key to promoting common European values, fostering social integration, enhancing intercultural understanding, and building a sense of belonging within the European society. Una Europa has already identified several mobility formats, from virtual mobility, and blended mobility to physical mobility.

The Vision and Action Plan on Mobility also addresses the key areas of the Una Europa R&I strategy as well as the core values of our research community: accessibility for all and inclusiveness. The vision emphasises the traditional academic staff mobility for teaching and training within the Alliance, the joint training activities for early researchers, as well as the continuous professional development of the Una Europa professional community and its importance for the R&I capacity building. The vision also presents institutional actions to enhance the capacity of investing in mobility opportunities at each Una Europa university. The next step is to identify external funding opportunities to enable mobility including regional funds and European funding schemes such as Erasmus+. The plan will undergo a mid-term review in November 2024 to check the feasibility and level of development of each action/activity foreseen. We suggest doing this in-line with the Una Europa R&I roadmap process.

Based on the insights collected during the R&I Strategy development, we want to outline the importance of dedicated mobility funding for unlocking the potential behind physical gatherings of the Una Europa academic community. This is an essential element in building trust-based relationships and long-term deep research collaborations across disciplines, institutions, and countries. In addition to exploring external funding opportunities, partner universities are encouraged to set up internal funding mechanisms for mobility to enhance the Una Europa research collaboration. The mechanisms should include both well-coordinated processes and communication about the external opportunities as well as possible internal mobility budget for the Una Europa activities to make mobility of our academics and professional staff as smooth as possible. The priority target groups should be the academics in the SSCs and Focus Areas, especially early-career researchers, and the research professionals in the thematic task forces and clusters (described below). The mobility funding can include short- and long-term visits as well as support for organising events aimed at interdisciplinary matchmaking. It is important to recognise that the funding pathways of the two target groups, academics and professionals, differ.

In addition, Una Europa aims to create an Una Europa-Africa Fellowship programme to invest in longer-term mobility opportunities for proven connections across the partnership, in specific areas of research. The Alliance will explore funding opportunities to fulfil this most welcomed strategic initiative.

Investing in Digitalising Collaboration

Una Europa has committed to investing in an online community building platform, which will enable community building through digital collaboration, document management and project management functionalities and will include a space for internal communications. The platform will serve the needs of academic staff, as well as professional staff and students. However, essential digital tools for facilitation of the collaborative research in our Alliance have not been included so far as part of the scope of the platform currently developed, but will require urgent additional investments.

To address direct research-related needs, Una Europa should leverage commercially available platforms for collection of expressions of interest for higher education consortium building and subsequent matchmaking. In addition, the Alliance should further develop its website for providing information about the research portals of the partners universities to aid in identifying potential collaborators and for communication about funding opportunities. Furthermore, a platform should be created to share online training courses for researchers and research professionals. The tools themselves can be chosen cost-efficiently. Yet, coordinating usage, producing contents, and facilitating on-line events and workshops requires substantial work and expertise. Una Europa thus needs to address human resourcing for this task both on Alliance and institutional level.

In the medium term, we require a tool for sharing information on research and data infrastructures. In the long term, we aim to further facilitate efficient matchmaking between researchers, research groups, and interdisciplinary units by developing AI-based tools that collect data from our partner universities' research portals, also addressing the legal barriers. The latter could also be implemented as a research project to produce research knowledge for the best of Europe.

Recognition of the Clusters of Research Professionals

The successful implementation of the Strategy will depend upon academics and professionals collaborating across our distinctly strong partner universities. The Una Europa clusters, which are staffed by experts on specific themes, provide the backbone of expertise and support for our joint activities. Proving the value of this innovative format, the clusters have been central to establishing Una Europa and its values at our partner institutions and will continue to play a crucial role in the implementation of the R&I Strategy including the transversal themes like Open Research, Citizen science and collaboration with non-academic partners.

Our Alliance provides a possibility to deepen the international networks of our professional staff and create exceptional conditions for mutual learning and professional development. This in turn will strengthen our research capacities at the level of individual institutions and at the Alliance level, and even further at the ERA level. Joint training and peer-to-peer exchange of best practices are key parts of this process. Importantly, clusters enable smooth peer-to-peer communication at an Alliance level and internally at the partner universities, thus have a crucial role in communicating the Una Europa aims and opportunities. They also act as ad hoc advisory bodies for new initiatives and support their implementation. In some cases, clusters may have a specific role in implementing activities and outputs, in which case additional human and financial resources may be needed. In addition, the clusters have pivotal role in supporting the research community by providing input on jointly developed signature trainings on transversal themes such as open research and citizen engagement and support skills training related to research infrastructures. As an example, the Open Research Cluster has a pivotal role in mainstreaming Open research in the Alliance. While most of our partner universities already offer training programs on various priorities of the EU Open Science policy, such as the "Future of Scholarly Communication" (Open Access and funding), and "Open Data: FAIR Data" (data management and publishing), we recognise the need to refine and expand these programs through sharing best practices.

The need and tasks for certain thematic clusters are currently evaluated as part of the Una.Futura project. The Alliance aims to share principles for the clusters' operation. As general rule, the clusters work on a self-managing basis and are chaired by an appointed member who calls the meetings on a regular or ad-hoc basis. In addition to the clusters, smaller task forces of professionals, academics or both shall be set up to provide flexible and resource-saving support to the Una Europa initiatives when needed. Based on the Una Europa R&I strategy work, in addition to the current thematic clusters, it is worth considering how to connect experts on inter-, trans-, and multidisciplinary collaborative research to profit from the exceptional experience available at the partner universities.

As the clusters are integral to all Una Europa endeavours, the partner institutions pledge to support their aims and activities. Key managers, such as those overseeing administration, human resources, or relevant departments, are recommended to engage in yearly discussions regarding the clusters' primary activities and resource needs. This approach will not only keep partner universities informed about the clusters' work at the Alliance level, but also ensure that their efforts are in line with the universities' goals and resourcing plans. Additionally, if possible, cluster members' job descriptions should include a recognition of the cluster work.

Permanent Establishment of the Research Coordination Cluster

The Research Coordination Cluster (RCC) was formed to bring together research funding, research development, and policy experts from our partner institutions. The RCC's primary objective was to develop a comprehensive understanding of the research services provided by each partner university, serve as a basis for connecting expertise and enable seamless peer-to-peer communication both within the Alliance and internally at partner universities.

While the RCC will still have a significant role in connecting the expertise and allowing smooth peer-to-peer communication, going forward, the cluster will primarily focus on coordinating and facilitating matchmaking for interdisciplinary research funding calls. RCC will also coordinate sharing information concerning national career

opportunities and funding schemes. The on-line communications about the opportunities should be available for the whole community. However, the priority target groups for the RCC coordinated support should be the Una Europa Focus Area SSCs and the academics conducting Una Europa seed funding projects.

Given its vital role in facilitating research collaboration, the RCC will become a permanent Una Europa entity. The allocated working time of individual RCC members should consist of at least 5-10% of a full-time equivalent, depending on the commitment and involvement of the home university in the funding calls. The Una Europa Board of Directors (BoD) and Research Strategy Group (RSG) recommend that the allocated working time will be evaluated regularly to make sure that the time invested is sufficient to support vital matchmaking of our researchers.

Participation in the cluster should be included in the job description of the professionals, if feasible. Future cluster members should be experienced research funding professionals with extensive knowledge of their institutions, funding schemes, and institutional structures and strategic goals.

Investing in Seed Funding

The Una Europa Seed Funding scheme creates impact at the level of the Alliance, but also for the researchers involved and their institutions. It is a pivotal incentive for Una Europa's broad academic community for initiating long-term collaborative activities fertilising bold ideas to knowledge for the best of Europe and the world.

In the Una Europa R&I strategy process, the academics considered seed funding as one of the key tools to incentivise research collaboration. So far, our Alliance has launched 5 calls, and has funded 44 projects worth €679.645 in total. Several of these projects have led to successful joint applications for external follow-up funding, as well as the creation of joint formats such as joint courses, micro-credentials and summer/winter schools contributing directly to the Alliance's research and education offer. The latest 2022 call with a dedicated Chair and associated fellowship in each Focus Area particularly supports the development of Una Europa's focus areas into international hubs for research, education, and knowledge transfer.

The Una Europa seed funding is primarily targeted at small scale projects, still large enough, though, so that the efforts required for proposal evaluation are well invested. The Una Europa R&I strategy identifies several areas where the seed funding initiative should be further developed. First, seed funding is an essential tool for encouraging the broad community to come together to develop groundbreaking ideas in emerging research areas, thus the level of funding should be sufficient. Secondly, seed funding would benefit the preparations for Horizon Europe consortium calls, and thirdly the seed funding could be used for developing the transversal strategic areas such as open research, citizen engagement, and partnerships with the industry as well as Research infrastructure initiatives.

The Una Europa values for research and the R&I strategy goal for advancing bold interdisciplinarity collaborative research are well considered in the evaluation criteria of the proposals. In addition, in line with the R&I strategy's ambition to global collaboration, Una Europa aims to address specific budget for mobility of early-career researchers affiliated to African partner universities and provide opportunities to appoint chair holders from the African partner universities addressing the global nature of the Alliance.

The seed funding processes are currently being evaluated. In the coming years, Una Europa aims to launch annual seed funding calls. It is necessary to consider if the level of funding is sufficient considering the key function of seed funding for research community building. Until today, the funding has been appointed from the vzw budget. In the future, the Alliance should explore other seed funding sources and ways to overcome legal and organisational barriers to maximise the opportunities emerging out of this essential funding type.

Roadmap to Implementation

Annex 2, Una.Resin Project Deliverable D1.2

Final Version, 23rd June 2023; Lead Authors: Dr. Carolin F. Roeder (FUB) and Dr. Elina Tonteri (UH)

The Una Europa R&I Strategy defines three strategic areas of action. The ambitions within these three areas will be achieved by a series of concrete actions. This roadmap describes the three phases of the implementation process both retrospectively and forward looking, centering on the process of defining key activities and resources that will be implemented as part of the R&I Strategy in the near future.

Phase I: Identification

Phase I consisted of identifying concrete actions that could be taken to achieve our strategic aims as well as a process of structuring these actions in detail according to their level of ambition and required resourcing.

STAGE 1 May 2022 - June 2023

Stage 1 was completed during the initial phases of the strategy process. Through a variety of tools, formats, and modes of inquiry an extensive list of proposed activities and measures was compiled. These formats included (among others) a Research Strategy Workshop, an online survey of Una Europa community, the piloting of methods to accelerate cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration, and regular consultations with the chairs of the SSCs of the Una Europa Focus Areas, Una.Resin project leads, cluster members, the Una Europa BoD, and the RSG.

STAGE 2 May - June 2023

To structure the actions for the further implementation process, a matrix was developed in stage 2. The matrix maps out potential activities on strategic ambitions at the level of the Alliance, based on different levels of ambitions and required resources, with the aim to rank priority areas and activities for the next years. It presents each activity in terms of its level of ambition (low-ambition activities – medium-ambition activities – high-ambition activities) and level of internal investment required for their successful implementation (low resource – medium resource – high resource).

Phase II: Prioritisation

During phase two, a prioritisation of actions at the Alliance's highest decision-making level will take place. A dedicated online survey has been designed to allow partner universities to make strategic choices in an open and transparent manner. The survey will be run in two stages.

STAGE 1 June – October 2023

The first stage will focus on collecting priorities in relation to the proposed actions. It will be open from July 20th to September 15th, 2023. The outcomes of the exercise will be presented and discussed at a forthcoming virtual meeting of the RSG in October 2023. During this meeting, overall priorities will be agreed.

STAGE 2 October – November 2023

The second stage will focus on the level of ambition and resource to be allocated to the chosen priorities. Following the virtual meeting of the RSG in October 2023, when priorities have been agreed, a second survey will be circulated for each partner university to define the preferred level of ambition and resources that they would like to allocate to the agreed R&I prioritised set of actions.

Phase III: Implementation

Phase three foresees the implementation of those activities selected as priorities in the previous phase. Actions will be taken either in the framework of Nonfuture through the SSC strategies and action plans or, depending on the nature of action, as a project-independent all-Alliance activity guided by the Una Europa R&I Strategy and the Una Europa 2030 Strategy.

STAGE 1: November 2023

The outcomes of the matrix exercise will inform the development of a common R&I action plan for the Alliance. The preliminary action plan will be presented and discussed at the BoD and RSG meeting that will be organised within the closing Una.Resin event, which will take place in Brussels on November 22nd, 2023.

STAGE 2: December 2023 – December 2030

Based on a clear agreement between the partners on the prioritised actions and resources to be committed, actions will be either implemented under the framework of Una.Futura, with institutional resources, or with institutional resources focused on attracting external funding. The Investment Pathway (Annex 1) will serve as guidance in this process. Activities that were not selected as priorities will remain accessible in a shared document for later consideration. The Una Europa 2020 Strategy provides the timeframe of the implementation process from now until 2030.

